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Effects Of Frequency Of Practice On Achievement Of Junior Secondary Students' In Essay Writing In Taraba State, Nigeria.

¹Olayinka Mojisola Iyekekpolo; ²Chinwe A. Muodumogu & ³Josephine U, Akabogu

¹Lecturer, Arts Education Department, English language unit,
Taraba State University, Jalingo, Nigeria
yinkaivekekpolo@gmail.com; 07035828123 (corresponding author)

²Professor of language Education,
Department of Arts Education,
Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria
08065641445

³Professor, English language Education;
Head, Department of Arts Education,
University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria
uzoakabogu@gmail.com 08035458263

ABSTRACT

The study examined effects of frequency of practice on Junior Secondary Two students' achievement in essay writing. The study which adopted non-randomized pre-test, post-test quasi experimental design was guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. The population of the study comprised of 726 JS2 students in the eight-co-educational public Junior secondary schools in Wukari township. A sample of three public schools and 62 JS2 students were purposively selected for the study. Instrument for data collection was English Writing Achievement Test (EWAT). Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed among others that frequency of practice enhanced students' achievement in essay writing significantly. The study therefore recommended that students be engaged in series of essay writing practice in order to become effective writers. Feedback was recommended as a constant feature of writing exercises while being a male or female was discovered not to be a significant factor in essay writing achievement among Junior secondary students.

Keywords: frequency of practice, achievement in essay writing

INTRODUCTION

Writing is putting down on paper one's thoughts, ideas, feelings, response or reactions about a particular issue or topic. Writing has been defined in various ways. Aliyu (2010) says it is a sustained form of putting down impressions, statements or declarations. According to Chukwuma and Otagburuagu (2008) writing is a piece of continuous prose that develops a point of view on a given topic. Offorma (2004) cited in Offorma (2009) describes it as a language skill that is purposive and requires that the writer makes use

of correct grammar, spelling and punctuation. It is creating meaningful texts such as stories, descriptions, invitations or informative pieces which help to develop comprehension and composing skills as well as promote spelling and decoding skills (Oyetunde & Muodumogu, 1999). It is one of the basic language skills and Offorma (2009) sees it as the highest and most complex of these skills. Other language skills are listening, speaking and reading, however, the writing skill reflects the extent to which an individual has become proficient in other language skills, the English language.

Writing exists in various forms, ranging from narrative, descriptive, expository to argumentative. The external examinations (West African School Certificate Examination and National Examination Council) which students write at the end of secondary education, cover a wide range of tests of writing skills in the four types of writing: The purpose of these writing tests is to ascertain students' ability to use English Language as an effective means of communication in any given situation. The English language writing tests is allocated very high marks in external examinations. It attracts fifty marks, while other aspects of English Language paper I (Essay) which are comprehension and summary, attract twenty and thirty marks respectively (WAEC, 2023). It has been observed that teachers do not make deliberate efforts at the teaching of writing skill in English language at the Lower Basic Level of education in Nigeria (Akabogu & Iyekekpolor, 2023).

The methods employed in the teaching of writing have yielded little results as students' inability to communicate effectively in writing has continued to lead to their poor performance in examinations. The percentage pass of students at the senior secondary certificate examinations (SSCE) organized by the West African Examination Council (WAEC) published by Chief examiner's report has been poor evident in the following: 34.75%, 36.14%, 39.4%, 42.6%, 43.8%, 46.3%, 47.2%, 48.3%, 49.4%, 52.93%, 59.2%, 65.24%, 81.7% and 76.36% in 2009 – 2022 respectively (WAEC, Chief examiner's report 2009-2022). Basic Education (BECE) results in English language supplied by the Taraba State Ministry of Education reveal 66.68% in 2020 and a lower performance in 2023 which was 62.5%. The poor performance recorded over the years, is an indication that teachers need to explore better ways of teaching writing in order to attain a hundred percent achievement. The study is based on J.B. Watson behaviourist theory of 1913. The theory is of the view that learning that is based upon the belief that all behaviours are acquired through conditioning. Frequency of writing is the instrument for conditioning of students in the writing class in the present study.

Frequency of Practice is the engagement of students in constant essay writing with essential activities of process writing. Spandel and Stiggins (1990) say good and frequent assessment should be an integral part of the writing process – not interference and not just an end-of-the-line step. Obah (2009) is of the view that the ability to write well is an acquired skill gotten through painstaking effort. Learning to write well therefore takes time and practice. Di Yanni and Hoy II (1995) are of the opinion that learning and writing go hand in hand. To accumulate knowledge about how to write well, the knowledge must be deliberately acquired by way of experience – that is by frequent writing exercises. Muodumogu (2010) is also of the view that for students to become writers, they need to write regularly and that students who write infrequently cannot develop fluency in writing.

The purpose of frequency of practice is to develop in students the art of writing. It is a form of assessment in itself. It is a means of checking what a student can do with the language he has learnt. Aristotle propounded the rhetorical theory, according to the theory, to write is to invent, that is to discover the subject matter (Olukpe, 1979). The subject matter will be discovered when students are asked to write on different topics. Two principles important for learning are repetition and reinforcement. Good and acceptable responses from students are to be repeated and the students further encouraged by the teacher to bring in excellence. When there is reinforcement, students gain better understanding of the relationship between efforts they have made in writing and their achievement eventually (Robbinson, 2009). Williams (1999) says students in the composition class must be given motivation for the writing they are required to do.

The process approach to writing is a step by step procedure involving the learners in the different phases of the writing process. It creates the opportunity for the learner to practice the pre-writing, writing and re-

writing activities and by so doing imbibe the writing skill (Offorma, 2009). This method is similar to guided or controlled writing (Uzoegwu, 1995; Ejembi, 2002), Akuma, 2006). It is interactive and involves the active participation of the teacher and the learners as they work through the phases (Offorma, 2009). Guth (1988) observes that good writing is the result of a process that moves through overlapping stages which are guided by purpose of writing, gathering of what to write, shaping what is to be finally presented through revision, editing and proofreading.

One common mistakes made by students in essay writing is misunderstanding the task which has been set and therefore not answering the question which has been asked. Ulliong (2012) says inability to write essays in a well-developed paragraphs, wrong tenses, failure to hyphenate compound words, omission or wrong use of verbs, nouns, articles, prepositions and adjectives, use of capital letters in addresses, doting of personal pronoun 'I', the use of small letters to begin a sentence or new paragraph; poor spellings, lack of consistency in the use of either the letters, use of abbreviation, slangs and greetings in formal letter are errors frequently made by students. He further states that students are not able to differentiate between article writing and letter writing. Students engage in construction of loose, wrong insertion or omission of the apostrophe, use of cardinal numbers to write date in address, failure to punctuate addresses properly or no punctuation at all, use of capital letters to write all the words in an address. Others are addition of an apostrophe with 's' in the complementary close of a letter, failure to use past tense to narrate events, faulty separation of words, inability to use vocatives in argumentative essay and the use of short message service(sms) abbreviations in essay writing are all evidences of the poor performance of students in continuous writing.

Generally, in African culture women are often rated as being lower than the men particularly in the area of this study. The African culture recognizes frequently the supremacy of men over women. Various studies have been carried out on the effect of gender on students' performance and achievement. Some scholars conclude that boys appear to be pro-science and technology and girls appear to be pro-art. Ability has been defined as the natural tendency to do something successfully. It is a natural gift for doing something. Students have varying cognitive abilities. There are low, medium and high levels of abilities in students (Adebile & Alabi, 2007). This study examined the contribution of abilities of students to their achievement in essay writing.

Ijiga (2009) investigated the relationship between students' verbal ability and their achievement in reading comprehension and the interaction effect of verbal ability and gender on students' achievement in reading comprehension. The study adopted a descriptive Ex-post Factor design. A total of 1,500 students drawn from 30 secondary schools in Otukpo local government area of Benue State served as population of the study. Two research instruments were used to elicit information from respondents. They were Reading Comprehension Achievement Test (RCAT) and Verbal Ability Test (VAT). The findings showed that students' verbal ability has a relationship with their achievement in reading comprehension. It was therefore recommended that instructional strategies should be explored to facilitate students' verbal ability so as to endure their achievement in reading comprehension. This study will look into the effect of students' reasoning ability on their achievement in essay writing as verbal ability was discovered to have effect on students' achievement in comprehension.

Muodumogu (2010) carried out a study to find out the extent to which teachers' writing assessment practice enhance learners' writing effectiveness, to what extent their assessment tasks enhance students' creativity and to what extent teachers adopt scoring/grading methods that bring to the awareness of the students their needs in writing. A total of 75 schools randomly selected from rural and urban areas in Benue State were involved in the study. A post-hoc analysis survey method based on already existing records in students' exercise books was used to collect data from 150 classes. The findings revealed that teachers scoring methods do not inform learners of their writing needs. It was also discovered that teachers writing assessment practices contradicts the principle of teaching writing as a process and as a matter of fact, teachers' writing assessment practices fall below expectation. The study reveals that teachers' assessment practices has not been able to train students to self-assess their writing in order to

become independent writers. In this present study, there is an attempt at making students become independent writers through placing the scoring criteria in their hands prior to writing.

Adeyemo (2010) conducted a study on Students' ability level and their competence in problem-solving task in Physics. A total of 200 randomly selected senior secondary school students were selected from Kosofe local government area of Lagos, Nigeria for the study. Instrument for data collection were students' questionnaire and students' achievement test. Data collected were analysed using simple regression analysis. The study revealed that students' ability has significant influence on problem-solving tasks in Physics. Teachers therefore need to be trained to acquire skills that will enable them develop teaching strategies that will facilitate development of students' problem solving ability.

A study was carried out by Akinwamide (2012) on the influence of process approach on English as second language students' performances in Essay Writing. The purpose of the study was to determine how far this approach could be of assistance to the writing skill development of the Nigerian child. The study employed the pre-test and post-test control quasi-experimental research design using a sample of eighty Senior Secondary three students. The researcher utilized the West African English Language Essay Questions as an adapted instrument to gather data. Statistical results showed a significant difference in the post-test scores of the experimental and the control groups. The process approach had significant effect on students' overall performance in essay writing. The approach was discovered to be of pedagogic reward, and a revealing and reliable method in the development of the writing skill. This study examined the effect of step by step approach in the teaching of writing of students' achievement in essay writing. It also examined the effect of writing rubric by WAEC on students' achievement in essay writing.

The work of Achor and Agamber (2016) the study examined if frequency of practical work has effect on psychomotor skill acquisition of senior secondary two (SS2) biology students. A sample of (N = 228 students from 3 government approved schools in Konshisha local government area of Benue State Nigeria was used. Biology Achievement Test (BAT) with reliability coefficient of 0.89 was used to collect data from students in Biology. Mean and standard deviations were used to answer research questions while Analysis of Covariance was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. ANCOVA with the P-value of less than 0.05 for achievement ($F_{2, 221}=240.521, p<0.05$) among the harmonized, intermediate and the control groups showed that there was significant difference in achievement. No significant difference was observed between boys and girls in the intermediate ($F_{1, 278}=0.015, p>0.05$) and the harmonized ($F_{1, 65} = 3.248, p>0.05$) groups. It is recommended that among others that teachers should endeavour to organize practical work for students as frequently as possible so as to develop in the student the practical skills required for final examination and other career development in life. This research might bring about an improvement in students' essay writing ability.

The study of Onyedikachi, (2021) examined influence of gender discrimination on students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. The study which adopted a descriptive research design was guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. A total of 400 students were drawn through stratified and simple random sampling technique from a population of 21,900 students and staff of all the SS1 and SS II in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. Instrument for data collection was a researcher structured 30-item questionnaire patterned towards 4-point rating scale. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that there was gender discrimination which influenced students' academic achievement and students' subject selection. The study concluded that gender discrimination has negative influence on students' academic achievement, with the female gender at the receiving end.

A study carried out by Jia (2022) on influence of age on learning effectiveness of English second language focused on critical period hypothesis (CPH). The study which emphasised that there exists a limited and specific period for language acquisition explored the relationship between language learners' starting age, in other words the chronological age at which an individual begins to learn a second language and academic achievement. A total of 191 students within the age of 7-9 were involved in the study. Data was collected with the use of interviews and examinations. The examination questions

consisted of sound discriminations exercises, listening tests, reading, punctuation and grammar. Pearson correlation statistic was used to analyse data. Findings from the study revealed that the age at which an individual begin to learn the second language affects achievement as learners whose starting age was younger had more advantages than those whose starting age was older.

Examining the relationship between English as a foreign language learners' cognitive abilities and L2 grit in predicting their writing performance was carried out by Zhang & Zhang (2023). The study was designed to find out the interplay among English as a foreign language learners' cognitive abilities and grit in predicting writing performance along different task complexity through path analysis and multiple group analysis. Respondents in the study were 353 tertiary students from Western China. Working memory capacity and language aptitude of the students were evaluated through argumentative and narrative writing tasks given to students. The study revealed that perseverance of effort and working memory on L2 writing performance were significant in argumentative writing while a positive predictive effect of working memory capacity was discovered on L2 learners' writing performance in complex tasks. The study under review is similar to the present study because working memory is a manifestation of cognitive ability that is tested in the present study.

Statement of the problem.

Several efforts have been made to help students overcome their poor writing ability in English Language. Some of these efforts focus on identifying factors responsible for the mass failure and recommending possible methods of teaching essay writing effectively. These methods have yielded little results as students' inability to communicate effectively in writing has continued to lead to poor performance in examinations.

How then can students be helped to discover areas of shortcomings in their writings in order to address them? How can students be guided to anticipate exactly what the examiners expect and prepare adequately before their examination through frequent practice in essay writing?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to find out the effects of frequency of practice on achievement of Junior secondary students' in essay writing in Taraba state, Nigeria.. The specific objectives were to:

1. Find out effects of frequency of practice on writing achievement on Junior secondary two students.
2. Establish the effect of frequency of writing practices on male and female students' achievement in writing
3. Ascertain the effect of frequency of practice on high and low ability students' writing

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

- RQ₁ What is the effect of frequency of practice on writing achievement of Junior secondary two students?
- RQ₂ To what extent does frequency of practice affect male and female students' achievement in writing?
- RQ₃ What is the effect of frequency of practice on writing achievement of high and low ability students?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

- Ho1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students exposed to frequency of practice and students exposed to rubrics.
- Ho2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to frequency of essay writing practices.
- Ho3. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of low and high ability students exposed to frequency of essay writing practices.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a pre-test, post-test quasi experimental design. The population for study was made up of 726 Junior secondary two students drawn from the eight co-educational schools. Purposive sampling method was used draw 62 students from three classes in three secondary schools were involved in the study. Data was collected using Essay Writing Achievement Test (EWAT). The instrument yielded a reliability value of which yielded a reliability of 0.69. Pre-test took place in week 1 and treatment began in earnest for the groups; at the end of the third week, a post test was carried out. The mean of the pre-test scores and the mean of the post-test scores were compared. The pre-test was used to ascertain the students' achievement in writing before the intervention programme. The post-test mean score of the three groups were compared, the post- test mean score of the male and female students were compared and the mean score of the students was also compared with respect to their ability levels. Existing score records of students in their various schools was used to divide them into ability levels. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The hypotheses were tested at 0.5 level of significance using Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) statistic.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Data were analysed based on research questions and hypotheses. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 significant levels.

Research Question One: *To what extent would the mean achievement scores of students exposed to writing rubrics and those exposed to frequency of practice differ?*

Treatment Groups		Pretest	Posttest	Mean Gain
Writing rubric group	Mean	3.83	4.89	1.06
	N	18	18	
	Std.D	2.176	2.564	
Frequency of Practice in essay Writing group	Mean	4.29	20.18	15.89
	N	17	17	
	Std.D	5.205	13.347	

Table 1 shows that the prior knowledge of writing rubrics group had a pre-test mean score of 3.83 and post-test mean score of 4.89 with a mean gain of 1.06. The students exposed to frequency of practice in essay writing group had a pre-test mean score of 4.29 and a posttest mean score of 20.18. This shows that students exposed to frequency of practice in essay writing achieved higher than students exposed to writing rubrics.

Research Question 2: *In what manner would frequency of practice and gender affect students' mean achievement in essay writing?*

Table 2: Mean Achievement scores of male and female students in frequency of practice group

Gender		Pre test	Post test	Mean Gain
Male	N	11	11	
	Mean	2.91	18.18	15.27
	Std.D	3.590	14.483	
Female	N	6	6	
	Mean	6.83	23.83	17
	Std.D	6.998	11.215	

Table 2 shows that the male students had a pre -test mean score of 2.91 and post- test mean score of 18.18 with a mean gain of 15.27. The female students had a pre -test mean score of 6.83 and a post -test mean score of 23.83 with a mean gain of 17. It therefore means that the female students achieved higher than their male counterpart.

Research Question 3: *In what way, would frequency of practice and students' ability affect their mean achievement scores in essay writing?*

Table 3: Mean achievement scores of high and low ability students in frequency of practice group.

Ability		Pre test	Post test	Mean Gain
High	N	10	10	
	Mean	6.20	26.60	20.4
	Std.D	5.673	12.149	
Low	N	7	7	
	Mean	1.57	11.00	9.43
	Std.D	3.047	9.309	

Table 3: reveals that the high ability students had a pre -test mean score of 6.20 and post-test mean score of 26.60 with a mean gain of 20.4. The low ability students had a mean score of 1.57 and 11.00 in their pre -test and post -test respectively with a mean gain of 9.43. This reveals that the high ability students achieved higher than the low ability students.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students exposed to frequency of practice and students exposed to prior knowledge of writing rubrics.

Table 4:

(i) Treatment Groups	(j) Treatment Groups	Mean differenc e (I – J)	Std Error	Sig ^a	95% confidence Interval for a Differences	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Writing rubric group	Frequency of practice in essay writing group	-14.544	2.046	.000	-19.588	-9.500

There is a significant difference in the mean achievement score of students exposed to frequency of practice in essay writing and students exposed to prior knowledge of writing rubrics at $P = .000 < .05$.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to frequency of essay writing practice.

Table 4: ANCOVA of frequency of practice group

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	2098.244a	4	524.561	8.368	.002
Intercept	1001.003	1	1001.003	15.969	.002
Pre	1006.073	1	1006.073	16.050	.002
Ability	118.669	1	118.669	1.893	.194
Gender	8.396	1	8.396	.134	.721
Ability *	34.763	1	34.763	.555	.471
Gender					
Error	752.227	12	62.686		
Total	9771.000	17			
Corrected Total	2850.471	16			

a. R squared = .736 (Adjusted R. Squared = .648)

Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female students exposed to frequency of practice in essay writing, since P is greater than .05 hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement score of low and high ability students exposed to frequency of practice in essay writing. Table 4 shows that the F value for ability is 1.893 at P = .194. Since P is greater than .05, it means that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of high and low ability students exposed to frequency of practice in essay writing.

Findings

The results revealed that:

1. Frequency of practice enhanced students’ achievement in essay writing.
2. Gender did not play a significant role in students’ achievement in essay writing.
3. The ability levels of students have proved not to be of significant effect in essay writing achievement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were

1. Teachers of English language should engage students in series of essay writing practice before they face examinations.
2. Students of both genders should be seen in the same light and be treated as such in the classroom and educational society
3. Teachers of English language should identify the strength and weaknesses of each student and manipulate such quality or inadequacy to create an encouraging environment through the use of teaching aids.

CONCLUSION

This study was an attempt at contributing to the success of students in English language particularly bringing about an improvement in students’ achievement in essay writing with the introduction of frequency of practice in essay writing. It was also discovered that gender was not a significant factor in

students' achievement in essay writing while positive effort by the teacher on a student of initial low ability can bring about an achievement that is beyond expectation.

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